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Comparative Contents Analysis of Selected Nigerian University Libraries' Websites

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Abstract:

The study underscored the need to periodically conduct contents analysis of Nigerian university library websites. Content of websites is supposed to be dynamic and episodic analysis assists in overcoming their weaknesses and challenges which ensure improved quality that meets web ranking metrics. Therefore employing qualitative research approach and case study methodology, 42 (25%) Nigerian university library websites were purposively and proportionately selected for the study using stratified sampling technique. Using a modified checklist of Mehta and Trivedi (2015) prepared from quality models and WCAG, data was collected directly from the websites. The data collected was analyzed using ATLAS for Window and Mac Qualitative Data Analysis Software. The results of the data analysis show that although significant number of the selected Nigerian university library websites are well structured and possessed basic information yet there are still many features and information that are absent in many of the websites. Also many of the websites are small and limited in scope, with most consisting of a single webpage or two to four interlinked pages, presenting their messages up-front instead of encouraging navigation through the sites. The research recommends among others the need for Nigerian university libraries, while improving their websites so that users may get requisite information without facing any inconvenience.

Keywords: Academic libraries; Contents analysis; Nigerian universities; websites

Introduction

Websites have not only come to replace the P.M.B. and P.O. Box as means of communication but as a collection of related network web resources. Websites can typically be dedicated to a particular topic or purpose, such as educational, news, entertainment, advertisement, etc. The web pages of websites are usually hyperlinked and the hyperlinking between web pages conveys to the reader the site structure and guides the navigation of the site, which often

starts with a home page containing a directory of the site web content.

Websites have today, doubtlessly, become the most important element of the internet and means of communication. Many organizations and institutions, such as universities and libraries have fully developed and deployed the use of websites for communicating their activities and other functions to the university community members and the general public. Individual, universities, libraries and other organizations websites can display information

contents such as texts, images, and videos about themselves, products and services on the internet.

Academic libraries according to Pareek and Gupta (2013) are nowadays using web environment to provide high-quality information for their users mostly in digital format. Similarly, Ward and Mervar (2003) stated that a library's website has now become a powerful gateway that can provide information to patrons. Collaborating this, Mehta and Trivedi (2015) stated that libraries websites could be used to increase visibility, raise levels of information literacy and deliver a personalized service that anticipates the current and future need of the users. They further argued that websites, particularly library's website had changed the impression of "traditional" and scholarly visits to physical libraries with modern aged virtual libraries on desktop access to library resources and services available. Using library websites, users can now register, and access information resources, check-in and out, download and print information resources. They can equally socialize using social media like Facebook, Google+, Twitter and many other customized features. The librarians can also direct, instruct and disseminate information to users and general public through the websites, making the website a focal point for all the university stakeholders and a viable point of contact (Astani 2013), and thus promoting educational activities beyond its immediate vicinity and becoming an instrument of promotion and advertisement.

Many interesting studies have been carried out on universities websites. For instance, Kiyea and Yusuf (2014) evaluated the usability of selected Nigerian universities' websites, while Ohiha (2014) understudied the web portal usability among Nigerian university students using the University of Benin-Nigeria as a case study. Similarly, Olaleye, el tel (2018) made a comparative evaluation of the quality of Nigerian Universities Websites. Interestingly, perusing the literature further shows many studies have also been conducted on university libraries websites. Using a different checklist of the necessary information about library websites, Haneef and

Venugupal (2010) analyzed the contents of 28 national library websites in Asia. In the same way, Pareek and Gupta (2013) analyzed the content of 52 academic library websites in Rajasthan. While Mehta and Trivedi (2015) conducted contents analysis of university library websites of Central Universities of India and Savitha (2016) carried out a content analysis of deemed university library websites of Karnataka State. However, the literature perused unfortunately indicates the absence of studies on Nigerian university library websites. All the literature reviewed pointed out the need to continuously conduct contents analysis and evaluation of websites, particularly those of universities and libraries to significantly overcome their shortcomings and weaknesses and to assist them in meeting quality requirements and web ranking metrics.

The purpose of this study is to make available information on selected Nigerian university library websites and to carry out contents analysis of these websites with the view to providing much information on their contents, strengths, weaknesses and ways of improvement. Since the development of library web sites started in the 1990s, Brower (2004) noted that today, very few libraries are without a presence on the web. Therefore, as the numbers of university library websites continue to grow there is the need to periodically take inventory of their contents because according to Lee (2001) the designing of a library website is an evolutionary process and as they continue to develop so also their contents should not only continue to be analyzed but as Lee further suggested, website evaluation should be incorporated into general web management principles. Manhas (2015) averred that a site with excellent content and facilities will be wasted if the user cannot find and access the information or facilities that they want. Therefore providing the user with the abilities to find and retrieve information from a website with comfort and ease helps in building an audience for it. He concluded that without efficient and user-friendly navigation, the user is likely to get confused, lost, or frustrated and leave the site for good.

Objectives of the Study

The study is set to achieve the following objectives:

1. To identify the structure of the home pages of the selected Nigerian university library websites
2. To find out the basic information available on the selected Nigerian university library websites
3. To identify the type of information contents on the websites of the selected Nigerian university library websites
4. To find out the type of information services available on the selected Nigerian university library websites

Scope of the study

The study is limited to only contents analysis of the selected Nigerian university library websites; therefore, it is not an evaluation. Although the study is not an evaluation, certain guidelines and quality models suited for websites analysis in websites assessment standards were employed. For instance, some of the 12 guidelines which were organized into four principles Information Technology in developing web contents provided by Web Contents Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) were also adopted.

Methodology

The qualitative research approach was adopted and case study methodology used. Using this methodology, data was collected from the selected Nigerian university library websites. The total number of universities in the country is 170 according to the National University Commission (NUC) (2019). The number is made up of 43 Federal, 48 State and 79 private universities; this constitutes the population of the study. Stratified and purposive sampling technique was used to proportionately select 42 (25%) sample of the study. Using a modified checklist of Mehta and Trivedi (2015) prepared from quality models and WCAG, data was collected directly from the websites. The data collected was analyzed using ATLAS for Window and Mac Qualitative Data Analysis Software.

Data Analysis and Discussion

The data collected directly from the 42 Nigerian university library websites were analyzed and discussed in line with the objectives set out for the study. The first objective of the research aimed at identifying the structure of the home pages of the selected Nigerian universities library websites. To achieve this, the major links on the homepage contents of the websites were analyzed and the findings presented in table 5.1 below.

Table 5.1: Structure of Home Pages of Selected Nigerian Universities Library Websites

Structure of the home page	Nigerian Universities							
	Federal		State		Private		Total	
	Yes F (%)	No F (%)	Yes F (%)	No F (%)	Yes F (%)	No F (%)	Yes F (%)	No F (%)
Link of the library website on the University website	15(83.3)	3(16.7)	10(83.3)	2(16.7)	7(58.3)	5(41.7)	32(76.2)	10(23.8)
Link to the University Website on the library website	50(50)	50(50)	10(83.3)	2(16.7)	7(58.3)	5(41.7)	26(62)	16(38)
Presence of the University/library Logo	12(66.7)	6(33.3)	9(75)	3(25)	9(75)	3(25)	30(71.4)	12(28.6)
Quick links	10(55.6)	8(44.4)	7(58.3)	5(41.7)	8(66.7)	4(33.3)	25(59.5)	17(40.5)
Contact us	12(66.7)	6(33.3)	7(58.3)	5(41.7)	8(66.7)	4(33.3)	27(64.3)	15(35.7)

Activities	12(66.7)	6(33.3)	7(58.3)	5(41.7)	5(41.7)	7(58.3)	24(51.1)	18(42.9)
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The findings as reflected in the above table represent the directory of the Nigerian university library site web contents. The Home page of websites is supposed to convey information to the user and guides navigation. Therefore, the findings show that collectively all the Nigerian university library websites have the basic structures, with majority 32 (76%) having their websites link on the university websites. Similarly, 26 (62%) have the link of the university website on the library websites. This means that a user can easily get to the library through the university websites and vice-versa. This support Ćelić, Cuculić and Valčić, (2016) assertion that a good website design should enable fast, simple and effective interaction regardless of user's profile, knowledge and experience.

Although majority of the library have Quick link, Contact Us and Activities on their websites, still many ranging from 33% - 58% do not have. It's quite interesting to note that the Federal and State university library websites shared common

characteristics in the structure of their home pages. However, further analysis indicates that there is a little gap between Federal and State universities library websites on one hand and that of Private universities library websites on the other on the structures and the standardization of the home page. The private university library websites seem to be more colorful and having more improved designs. The finding of this objective of the research supports Yoo and Jin (2004) earlier finding that the critical features of an ideal home page are used relatively frequently but in less degree.

The second objective of the research seeks to find out the basic information available on the selected university library websites. To achieve this, a list of basic information that an academic website is supposed to have on their websites was crosschecked against the information contents of the selected library websites. The findings are presented in table 5.2 below.

Table 5.2: Basic Information available on the Selected Nigerian Universities Library Websites

Basic Information	Nigerian Universities							
	Federal		State		Private		Total	
	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No
	F (%)	F (%)	F (%)	F (%)	F (%)	F (%)	F (%)	F (%)
History/About Us	3(16.7)	15(83.3)	2(16.7)	10(83.3)	2(16.7)	10(83.3)	7(16.7)	35(83.3)
Chronology of University Librarians and other library staff	11(61.1)	7(38.9)	4(33.3)	8(66.7)	3(25)	9(75)	18(42.9)	24(57.1)
Vision/Mission	3(16.7)	15(83.3)	4(33.3)	8(66.7)	0(0)	12(100)	7(16.7)	35(83.3)
Sitemap/library Tour	1(5.6)	17(94.4)	0(100)	12(100)	1(8.3)	11(91.7)	2(4.8)	40.95.2
Date of update	0(0)	18(100)	0(0)	12(100)	1(8.3)	11(91.7)	1(2.4)	41(97.6)
Feedback	2(11.1)	16(88.9)	0(0)	12(100)	0(0)	12(100)	2(4.8)	40(95.2)
FAQ	4(22.2)	14(77.8)	2(16.7)	10(83.3)	0(0)	12(100)	6(14.3)	36(85.7)
Staff Directory/Profile	0(0)	18(100)	0(0)	12(100)	0(0)	12(100)	0(0)	100(100)

Announcement	1(5.6)	17(94.4)	1(8.3)	11(91.7)	0(0)	12(100)	2(48)	40(95.2)
Membership	2(11.1)	16(88.9)	1(8.2)	11(91.7)	0(0)	12(100)	3(7.1)	39(92.9)
Library Policies and Procedure	2(11)	16(88.9)	1(8.3)	11(91.7)	0(0)	12(100)	3(7.1)	39(92.9)
Annual Reports/Statistics	1(5.6)	17(94.4)	1(8.3)	11(91.7)	0(0)	12(100)	2(4.8)	40(95.2)
Ongoing Project	0(0)	18(100)	0(0)	12(100)	0(0)	12(100)	0(0)	42(100)
Library Rules	2(11.1)	16(88.9)	2(16.7)	10(83.3)	1(8.3)	11(91.7)	5(11.9)	37(88.1)
Library Hours	6(33.3)	12(66.7)	5(41.7)	7(58.3)	3(25)	9(75)	14(33.3)	28(66.7)
Guideline for access	4(22.2)	14(77.8)	0(0)	12(100)	0(0)	12(100)	4(9.5)	38(90.5)
Library bulleting	0(0)	18(100)	0(0)	12(100)	0(0)	12(100)	0(0)	100(100)

The result of the findings as presented in the above indicate that out of the seventeen lists of basic information an academic library website is supposed to provide, majority 40 (95%) of the Nigerian university library websites do not have the required basic information. It is surprising to find out that many of the university libraries studied, cutting across federal, state and private, do not have Vision/Mission, History/About us, Library policy/Procedures, Library opening hours/Library rules on their websites. 36 (86%) of university libraries studied do not have. This finding is similar to the finding of Menon and Moitra (2014) in which they described it as an extremely alarming because, as they note, the absence of FAQs poses a serious problem for the libraries. It is not always possible for all the users to physically visit the university to enquire. So a university must stress into these aspects to market it successfully

The absence of such basic information as sitemap, library tour, feedback, date of update, etc. in most of the library websites from this study which coincided with the finding of Menon and Moitra (2014) made the websites to be providing static information, leading them to liken the websites to "Billboard". They argue that because

the websites do not have interactive features, it would not be incorrect to say that this seems to defeat the very purpose of having a website. Users as prospective customers, while choosing among information, would hunt for interactive features rather than basic information provided.

According to Pareek and Gupta (2013), Web 2.0 a technology which is facilitating communication, information sharing, and collaboration on the web is now being used by libraries around the world. Therefore, Social media networking facilities such as Facebook, Twitter, etc. are today the best media vehicle for the promotion of libraries. Unfortunately, the absence of social media networking facilities in the websites of all the selected Nigerian university libraries depicts lack of dynamism of the websites. University library websites must employ the use of social media networking because youth are much closer to these sites and rely more on them than any other media.

The second objective of the researcher further analyzed the provision of the library administration organs on the university library websites. Library patrons must be informed of the various divisions and their functions so that when they need information they will know where to

get. Given this, the websites were crosschecked to home page. Table 5.3 below shows the findings. find out the links to divisions provided on the

Table 5.3: Provision of Links to Division of the Library on the Selected Nigerian Universities Library Websites

Administration of the Library	Nigerian Universities							
	Federal		State		Private		Total	
	Yes F (%)	Not F (%)	Yes F (%)	No F (%)	Yes F (%)	No F (%)	Yes F (%)	No F (%)
Satellite/branch libraries	3(16.7)	15(83.3)	1(8.3)	11(91.7)	1(8.3)	11(91.7)	5(11.9)	37(88.1)
Collection Development Division/section	3(16.7)	15(83.3)	2(16.7)	10(83.3)	0(0)	12(100)	5(11.9)	37(88.1)
Resources Processing Division/section	3(16.7)	15(83.3)	3(25)	9(75)	0(0)	12(100)	6(14.3)	36(85.7)
Reference Service Division/section	3(16.7)	15(83.3)	3(25)	9(75)	0(0)	12(100)	6(14.3)	36(85.7)
Circulation Division/section	3(16.7)	15(83.3)	1(8.3)	11(91.7)	0(0)	12(100)	4(9.5)	38(90.5)
Reserved Division/section	3(16.7)	15(83.3)	0(0)	12(100)	0(0)	12(100)	3(7.1)	39(92.9)
Serial Division/section	3(16.7)	15(83.3)	1(8.3)	11(91.7)	0(0)	12(100)	4(9.5)	38(90.5)
E-library Division/section	4(22.2)	14(77.8)	1(8.3)	11(91.7)	1(8.3)	11(91.7)	6(14.3)	36(85.7)
ICT Division	3(16.7)	15(88.3)	1(8.3)	11(91.7)	1(8.3)	11(91.7)	5(11.9)	37(88.1)
Government Publication	3(16.7)	15(88.3)	0(0)	12(100)	0(0)	12(100)	3(7.1)	39(92.9)
Research and Bibliography	3(16.7)	15(88.3)	1(8.3)	11(91.7)	0(0)	12(100)	4(9.5)	38(90.5)
Media Division	3(16.7)	15(83)	1(8.3)	11(91.7)	0(0)	12(100)	4(9.5)	38(90.5)
Special Division	3(16.7)	15(83.3)	0(0)	12(100)	0(0)	12(100)	3(7.1)	39(92.9)

Table 5.3 above illustrates the types of division or section in a typical academic library. Big academic libraries may in addition to the listed divisions have satellite or branch libraries within or in other campuses of the university in which case the main library website should be able to link up the user to the webpage and contents of the satellite or branch libraries. It is believed that all the libraries studied have these divisions physically but unfortunately majority of them did not reflect them on their websites. Further investigation shows that the few that indicated their presence, the links are without contents. The finding also revealed that reserved division/section,

government publication and special division/sections were completely not available in the state and private university library websites.

It is very important that every library website includes information regarding its collection embracing different types of information resources such as books, journals, audio visual, etc. It is in light of this that another objective was formulated for the research to investigate the type of information contents available in the selected Nigerian university library websites. To achieve this, a list of information resources was cross-matched against those available on the websites and the results are as shown in table 5.4 below.

Table 5.4: The types of Information Contents on the Selected Nigerian Universities Library Websites

Library Collection	Nigerian Universities							
	Federal		State		Private		Total	
	Yes F (%)	Not F (%)	Yes F (%)	No F (%)	Yes F (%)	No F (%)	Yes F (%)	No F (%)
Books	2(11.9)	16(88.9)	1(8.3)	11(91.1)	1(8.3)	11(91.7)	4(9.5)	38(90.5)
Journals	2(11.1)	16(88.9)	0(0)	12(100)	0(0)	12(100)	2(4.8)	40(95.2)
Newspapers and Magazines	3(16.7)	15(83.3)	0(0)	12(100)	0(0)	12(100)	3(7.1)	39(92.9)
Reference resources	2(11.9)	16(88.9)	1(8.3)	11(91.1)	1(8.3)	11(91.7)	4(9.5)	38(90.5)
Audio Visual Material	1(5.6)	17(94.4)	0(0)	12(100)	0(0)	12(100)	1(2.4)	41(97.6)
Government Publications	2(11.1)	16(88.9)	0(0)	12(100)	0(0)	12(100)	2(4.8)	40(95.2)
Photograph	1(5.6)	17(94.4)	0(0)	12(100)	0(0)	12(100)	1(4.8)	41(95.2)
Special Collection	1(5.6)	17(94.4)	0(0)	12(100)	0(0)	12(100)	1(4.8)	41(95.2)

Although all the type of information resources listed in the above table is available in the libraries under study, it is rather strange to discover based on the obtained result that only a few libraries have them on their websites. This means that library clientele would still have to rely on physical resources because the information

on the websites is not adequate. The findings expose the silent weaknesses of the library websites confirming their non-interactive nature. The analysis covering the above objective of the research was further extended to non-book collections of the libraries. The result is as shown in table 5.5 below.

Table 5.5: The types of Non-Book Information Contents on the Selected Nigerian Universities Library Websites

Library Collection of Non-Book	Nigerian Universities							
	Federal		State		Private		Total	
	Yes F (%)	Not F (%)	Yes F (%)	No F (%)	Yes F (%)	No F (%)	Yes F (%)	No F (%)

Subscribed Databases	2(11.1)	16(88.9)	0(0)	12(100)	0(0)	12(100)	2(4.8)	40(95.2)
Open Access Databases	1(5.6)	17(94.4)	0(0)	12(100)	0(0)	12(100)	1(2.4)	42(97.6)
E-journal	9(50)	9(50)	4(33.3)	8(66.7)	4(33.3)	8(66.7)	17(40.5)	25(59.5)
CD Room Databases	9(50)	9(50)	4(33.3)	8(66.7)	4(33.3)	8(66.7)	17(40.5)	25(59.5)
E-books	9(50)	9(50)	8(66.7)	4(33.3)	4(33.3)	8(66.7)	21(50)	21(50)
Course/MOOCs	8(44.4)	10(55.6)	8(66.7)	4(33.3)	4(33.3)	8(66.7)	20(47.6)	22(52.4)
OPAC	12(66.7)	6(33.3)	0(0)	12(100)	2(16.7)	10(83.3)	14(33.3)	28(66.7)

Again, like the result of the printed collections, the non-book collection is no different. The result in the above table shows that very few library websites have links to subscribed and open access databases. In fact the state and private university libraries do not have at all. This indicates that Nigerian university libraries, especially state and private are yet to realize the need to host these important sources of information. The absence of OPAC on the websites of all the state university library websites is also clearly noticeable. Therefore, the absence of most of the non-book information resources on the websites of the selected Nigerian university libraries further make the websites static and non-interactive forcing the users to still rely more on the traditional library system.

Institutional Digital Repositories (IDRs) which aim at collecting the intellectual output that exists at a particular institution are institutional initiative that has proliferated academic libraries globally. Currently, more and more universities are developing archives to hold their faculty's publications and according to ACRL (2015) to provide open access to these intellectual contents as a way of disseminating and showcasing intellectual assets. It is in view of this that the above objective of the research further investigated the link and the contents of Institutional digital repository on the Nigerian University Library Website. The result is as shown in the table 5.6 below

Table 5.6: The types of Information Contents in the Institutional Repository on the Nigerian Universities Library Websites

Institutional Repository	Nigerian Universities							
	Federal		State		Private		Total	
	Yes F (%)	Not F (%)	Yes F(%)	No F (%)	Yes F (%)	No F (%)	Yes F (%)	No F (%)
Thesis/Dissertation	9(50)	9(50)	0(0)	12(100)	2(16.7)	10(83.3)	11(26.2)	31(73.8)
Staff Publication	8(44.4)	10(55.6)	0(0)	12(100)	2(16.7)	10(83.3)	10(23.8)	32(76.2)
University Publications	6(33.3)	12(66.7)	0(0)	12(100)	0(0)	12(100)	6(14.3)	36(85.7)
Convocation Lectures	4(22.2)	14(77.8)	0(0)	12(100)	1(8.3)	11(91.7)	5(11.9)	37(88.1)
Inaugural Lectures	4(22.2)	14(77.8)	0(0)	12(100)	1(8.3)	11(91.7)	5(11.9)	37(88.1)

Other publication	6(33.3)	12(66.7)	0(0)	12(100)	0(0)	12(100)	6(14.3)	36(85.7)
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The result from the table above shows that while few federal and fewer private university library websites have IDRs, very disturbingly none of the state university libraries has one. Analyzing the contents of those that have the repositories shows that only a few have theses/dissertation and staff publications. University publications such as convocation and inaugural lectures are not available. This is a great challenge looking at the importance of institutional repertory in ranking international institution. This finding clearly demonstrates the need for Nigerian university libraries to have their local contents hosted on their websites because apart from raising their

ranking, it will also increase their visibility and expose them to linkages and collaborations

The essence of the existence of any library is to offer services, no matter how good a library building, furniture or collection may be, without adequate provision of information services, the library may have no reason to exist. It is in view of this that an objective was formulated to investigate the information services available on the Nigerian university library websites. Thus, the websites of Nigerian university libraries were browsed to access a list of information services compiled by previous researches. The result is as indicated in the table below.

Table 5.7: The Type of Information Services Available on the Nigerian University Library Websites

Information Service	Nigerian Universities							
	Federal		State		Private		Total	
	Yes F (%)	Not F (%)	Yes F (%)	No F (%)	Yes F (%)	No F (%)	Yes F (%)	No F (%)
Current awareness service	1(5.6)	17(94.4)	0(0)	12(100)	0(0)	12(100)	1(2.4)	41(97.6)
Reference Service	1(5.6)	17(94.4)	0(0)	12(100)	0(0)	12(100)	1(2.4)	41(97.6)
Reference queries “ask a librarian “	1(5.6)	17(94.4)	0(0)	12(100)	0(0)	12(100)	1(2.4)	41(97.6)
Internet access service	1(5.6)	17(94.4)	0(0)	12(100)	0(0)	12(100)	1(2.4)	41(97.6)
Bibliography Services	1(5.6)	17(94.4)	0(0)	12(100)	0(0)	12(100)	1(2.4)	41(97.6)
Issue-return	1(5.6)	17(94.4)	0(0)	12(100)	0(0)	12(100)	1(2.4)	41(97.6)
OPAC	1(5.6)	17(94.4)	0(0)	12(100)	1(8.3)	11(91.7)	2(4.8)	40(95.2)
Information Search request	1(5.6)	17(94.4)	0(0)	12(100)	0(0)	12(100)	1(2.4)	41(97.6)
Renew material	1(5.6)	17(94.4)	0(0)	12(100)	0(0)	12(100)	1(2.4)	41(97.6)
Selection suggestion	1(5.6)	17(94.4)	0(0)	12(100)	0(0)	12(100)	1(2.4)	41(97.6)
User Guide of library classification	1(5.6)	17(94.4)	0(0)	12(100)	0(0)	12(100)	1(2.4)	41(97.6)
Material reservation	1(5.6)	17(94.4)	0(0)	12(100)	0(0)	12(100)	1(2.4)	41(97.6)
User education	0(0)	18(100)	0(0)	12(100)	0(0)	12(100)	0(0)	42(100)

The result of the findings with regards to the objective of the research as presented in the above table paints a very gloomy situation in the Nigerian university libraries. Although there are wide varieties in the spectrum of information services provided, the fact that as high as 41(97%) of the libraries not offering information services in the websites question the essence of establishing

the websites. The state and private university libraries are most affected in this regards with many of the information services missing on their websites. This finding conforms to Mundy and Musa (2010) finding in which they discovered that the content analysis carried out on state government websites demonstrate significant shortcomings.

Closely related to the issue of information services is the concept of value-added information services nowadays provided on websites. The value added information is that information that further markets the library. They are presented in summary and attractively to draw the attention of

the users, thereby motivating them to use the websites. To ascertain these value-added information services, the websites of the libraries were browsed to locate these types of information. Table 5.7 below illustrates the results.

Table 5.7: The Type of Information Services Available on the Nigerian Universities Library Websites

Value added Information and services	Nigerian Universities							
	Federal		State		Private		Total	
	Yes F (%)	Not F (%)	Yes F (%)	No F (%)	Yes F (%)	No F (%)	Yes F (%)	No F (%)
Image gallery of library	2(11.1)	16(88.9)	0(0)	12(100)	0(0)	12(100)	2(4.8)	40(95.2)
Library events calendar	0(0)	18(100)	0(0)	12(100)	0(0)	12(100)	0(0)	42(100)
Virtual help desk	0(0)	18(100)	0(0)	12(100)	0(0)	12(100)	0(0)	42(100)
Library blog	0(0)	18(100)	0(0)	12(100)	1(8.3)	11(91.7)	1(2.4)	41(97.6)
Library "news alert"	1(5.6)	17(94.4)	0(0)	12(100)	1(8.3)	11(91.7)	2(4.8)	40(95.2)
Library Newsletter	0(0)	18(100)	1(8.3)	11(91.7)	1(8.3)	11(91.7)	2(4.8)	40(95.2)
Social media network (Facebook)	3(16.7)	15(83.3)	2(16.7)	10(83.3)	0(0)	12(100)	5(11.9)	37(88.1)
Achievement	1(5.6)	17(94.4)	0(0)	12(100)	0(0)	12(100)	1(2.4)	41(97.6)

Based on the obtained results as presented in the above table, it can safely be concluded that majority of the value-added information services are not offered by federal, state and private university libraries. Only 2 and 3 federal university libraries provide gallery and social media services respectively. Library events calendar and virtual help desk links are completely absent in all the websites. Therefore, the absence of all of these further confirms an earlier contention that Nigerian university library websites are mere "Billboards".

Conclusion

The research concludes based on the results of the findings as discussed that a significant number of the selected Nigerian university library websites are small and limited in scope, with most consisting of a single webpage or two to four interlinked pages, presenting their message up-front instead of encouraging navigation through the sites. The static and non-

interactive nature of the selected Nigerian university library websites made them look like mere billboards

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this research, the following recommendations are put forward for implementation by the Nigerian university library websites:

- 1 Significant work still needs to be undertaken by the Nigerian university libraries to make their websites examples of 'best practice'
- 2 University library websites are supposed to be well-developed and complex, while improving their websites, it is recommended that an index page be introduced on their websites to assist in navigation.

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